

Determination of kinetic co-efficients of anaerobic treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater

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Abstract: A tubular anaerobic reactor of 10 L capacity was used to treat slaughterhouse wastewater under batch mode. It was operated with varying COD input under a constant batch detention time of 3 days over 210 days at the temperature $(37 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$. The reactor showed satisfactory performance, even under high COD input exerted by slaughterhouse wastewater. Maximum COD removal efficiency was recorded as 92.8% under a COD input of 7268 mg/L and biomass concentration of 33730 mg/L. Experimental results on COD removal were fitted in the Monod's growth kinetic model and kinetic co-efficients were determined with a good correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9181$). Maximum specific COD utilization rate (k) and half-velocity constant (K_s) of the anaerobic treatment were determined as 0.2539 g COD/g VSS/day and 1.302 g COD/L respectively, whereas yield coefficient (Y) and endogenous decay rate (K_d) were obtained as 0.239 g VSS/g COD removal and 0.013 g VSS/g VSS/day respectively.

Keywords: Slaughterhouse wastewater, anaerobic treatment, tubular anaerobic reactor, Monod kinetic model, kinetic co-efficients.

Introduction

Slaughterhouses produce meat and meat items for human consumption, organic solid waste and other by-products (skins, fats, and bones) along with considerable volumes of wastewater derived from cleaning operations. Inhibition in the anaerobic treatment of this wastewater with a high organic substance is generally exhibited by high ammonia concentrations^{1,2}, which is generated during degradation of proteins³. Slaughtered by-products are also rich in organic nitrogen since these may contain considerable amounts of undigested material, particularly if the cattle creatures are fed before slaughtering⁴.

The slaughterhouse wastewater contains high fat and protein, which make it a good substrate for the anaerobic digestion process. However, moderate hydrolysis rate and episode of inhibition have been reported in case of slaughterhouse wastewater. In particulate materials, e.g. animal by-products, hydrolysis progresses with the development of hydrolytic bacteria, and hence the overall degradation rate

is affected⁵. Besides, lipids can bring about biomass buoyancy and wash-out; and during lipid hydrolysis, Long-Chain Fatty Acids (LCFA) are generated by extracellular lipases. All these intermediate products have been identified as inhibitory species⁶. Additionally, ammonia is produced during protein degradation and its inhibitory impacts on anaerobic digestion (as NH_3) has also been accounted². Owing to those reasons and challenges of digestion as a unique substrate, industrial scale anaerobic digestion of animal by-products employs co-digestion with horticultural or domestic waste in centralized biogas plants⁷.

Kinetic modeling of the anaerobic treatment process is important for predicting performance and optimizing reactor design. The models on COD degradation revealed that the Monod kinetics was the best overall fit throughout the AD process. However, the reactions were best fit to first-order kinetics during the first ⁷⁻⁹ h and then best fit to higher order after about ⁸⁻¹³ h depending on initial COD

load⁸. Bhunia and Ghangrekar⁹ employed the Monod model, Haldane model, and Grau second order model to study the reactor performance and substrate removal for a synthetic wastewater with 0.3 to 4 g COD/L in a UASB system. It was concluded that Grau second-order model was the best fit ($R^2 = 0.98$) among abovementioned models for the performance evaluation and prediction. In a similar study, Sponza and Uluköy¹⁰ used the Monod model, Grau second-order model, and Stover-Kincannon model to evaluate reactor performance and substrate removal for a synthetic solution of 2,4-dichlorophenol with 6 to 44 g COD/L in a UASB system. In this case, Monod model showed the best fit ($R^2 = 0.95-0.98$) among the aforesaid models in the UASB reactor.

In a most recent study, Singh and Pandey¹¹ reported that there was 5% higher error in estimation by Anaerobic Digestion Model (ADM1) in comparison to that of Monod model. In spite of being an ancient mechanistic tool, Monod model still provides accurate results while compared to most developed computational models. In-depth literature review revealed that there was hardly any kinetic study pertaining to single-stage anaerobic treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the anaerobic biodegradability of typical raw slaughterhouse wastewater and also to estimate its kinetic coefficients using the experimental data.

Materials and methods:

Sample analysis:

Samples were analyzed for the parameters like pH, Total Solids (TS), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Mixed Liquor Suspended Solids (MLSS), Mixed Liquor Volatile Suspended Solids (MLVSS), Alkalinity, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Bio-chemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN), nitrates and phosphates, complying with Standard methods¹².

Fabrication of reactor setup:

The tubular anaerobic reactor was made of a 150 mm internal diameter and 5 mm thick acrylic fiber cylinder. A 10-mm inlet valve was placed at top of the reactor and the pipe was extended up to middle of the reactor. The gas outlet was placed at top plate of the anaerobic reactor, keeping 100 mm clearance.

The wastewater was fed into the reactor along bottom cross section, which helps to avoid short-circuiting of the influent from the sludge bed and to avoid formation of dead pockets at the bottom of the reactor. The effluent pipe was connected to a water seal arrangement to prevent escape of the gas through the effluent. Five sampling ports were installed along the length of each reactor at 10 cm intervals, starting from a height of 10 cm from the reactor bottom. The sampling ports of 8 mm internal diameter and 60 mm length were provided with brass nipples. A brass-made check valve of 20 mm dia. was fixed at the bottom of the reactors, to facilitate the sludge withdrawal. The biogas outlet was also provided at top of the gas head space of reactor. Biogas produced from the reactors was collected by water displacement method. For the sake of attaining completely mixed condition, one mechanical stirrer was provided centrally. A schematic diagram of the Tubular anaerobic reactor set-up is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the tubular anaerobic reactor set-up.

[Note: (1) Feed inlet, (2) Sampling ports, (3) Sludge withdrawal port, (4) Mixing stirrer, (5) Brine solution, (6) Measuring cylinder, (7) Gas releasing valve, (8) Seed sludge, (9) Gas conveyance tube, (10) Outlet].

Characteristics of wastewater:

The sample of slaughterhouse wastewater was collected from an abattoir located at Tangra, Kolkata. The collected wastewater was stored in a freezer at a low temperature of about 4°C. The characteristic of a slaughterhouse wastewater is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of slaughterhouse wastewater in this study

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value ^a	Std. deviation
1.	pH	7.4	0.105
2.	Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	242	38.57
3.	Total COD (mg/L)	8426	369.50
4.	Soluble COD (mg/L)	6294	184.75
5.	Total solids (mg/L)	16262	345.13
6.	Total dissolved solids (mg/L)	8980	688.77
7.	Total suspended solids (mg/L)	7281	980.04
8.	Total fixed solids (mg/L)	2767	233.51
9.	Total volatile solids (mg/L)	13495	114.23
10.	BOD ₃ at 27°C (mg/L)	5730	91.22
11.	Nitrogen (mg/L as N)	72	5.29
12.	TKN (mg/L as N)	426	8.00
13.	Phosphate (mg/L as P)	25	1.02
14.	Conductivity (ms/cm)	5.47	1.30
15.	Salinity (psu)	2.84	0.83

^aAverage of six samples.

Characteristics of digested sludge:

Anaerobic Digested Sludge was obtained from the biogas plant located at Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur, Kolkata. The plant is a conventional single stage anaerobic digester unit, which produces methane from cow dung slurry. Anaerobic Digested Sludge was taken from the bottom the sludge outlet tank. The characteristic of Anaerobic Digested Sludge is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of anaerobic digested sludge in this study

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value ^a	Std. deviation
1.	pH	6.9	0.95
2.	Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	555	32.71
3.	Total COD (mg/L)	2200	215.66
4.	Soluble COD (mg/L)		
5.	Total solids (mg/L)	36116	465.87
6.	Total dissolved solids (mg/L)	3028	894.51
7.	Total suspended solids (mg/L)	33087	1128.88
8.	Total fixed solids (mg/L)	10014	340.95
9.	Total volatile solids (mg/L)	26102	130.85
10.	BOD ₃ at 27°C (mg/L)	1540	58.40

^aAverage of three samples.

Reactor start-up:

The anaerobic reactor was initially filled with the 6 liters of the Anaerobic Digested Sludge collected from Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur. The digestion process started with a highly biodegradable synthetic wastewater, which was fed in gradually decreasing amount and the raw slaughterhouse wastewater was added to it in gradually increasing amount in a certain total volume of feed. Hence, a synthetic wastewater was prepared, which contained dextrose (C₆H₁₂O₆) as the substrate. The composition of synthetic wastewater is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Composition of synthetic wastewater

Sl. No.	Chemicals used	Amount (g/L)
1.	Dextrose anhydrous (C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆)	10.0
2.	Ammonium nitrate (NH ₄ NO ₃)	2.85
3.	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH ₂ PO ₄)	0.45
4.	Ferric chloride (FeCl ₃)	0.0250
5.	Magnesium sulphate (MgSO ₄)	0.0225
6.	Calcium chloride (CaCl ₂)	0.0275
7.	Phosphate buffer (KH ₂ PO ₄ .K ₂ HPO ₄)	0.0302

Batch acclimation study:

During acclimation period, the anaerobic reactor was added with a total volume of 500 ml feed for 10 cycles each comprising of 3 days. Hence, the amount of raw wastewater was increasing at 10% of total volume. i.e. 50 ml/cycle. The relative distribution of synthetic and raw wastewater in each cycle of acclimation is shown in Fig. 2. Under acclimation phase, initial and final pH as well as COD, MLSS, MLVSS and bio-gas (CH₄) were measured as monitoring parameters. After attaining 10th cycle, it was observed that the reactor could handle 500 ml raw wastewater feed satisfactorily. Therefore, batch kinetic study was initiated with gradually increasing amount of raw wastewater only.

Batch kinetic study:

In this stage, the volume of raw wastewater feed was started to increase @ 100 ml/cycle. This process was continued up to next 7 cycles under batch

Fig. 2. Relative distribution of synthetic and raw wastewater during acclimation process.

kinetic study to make a total volume of raw wastewater feed up to 1200 ml. After reaching this feed level the reactor was found to handle no more organic load per cycle of 3-days duration. Under batch kinetic study also, initial and final pH as well as COD, MLSS, MLVSS and biogas (CH₄) were measured as monitoring parameters.

Kinetic models used in anaerobic process:

To the best of current knowledge, kinetic modeling of single stage anaerobic reactor treating raw slaughterhouse wastewater is yet to be established. Therefore, in the present study, the highly appreciated and most frequently used Monod kinetic models were utilized under semi-batch mode. In accordance with this model the substrate utilization kinetics can be expressed as,

$$\frac{\theta X}{S_0 - S} = \left(\frac{K_s}{k}\right) \times \left(\frac{1}{S}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{K}\right) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the biomass growth kinetics can be established as,

$$\frac{X' - X}{\theta X} = Y \times \frac{S_0 - S}{\theta X} - k_d \quad (2)$$

where, S₀ = initial substrate concentration (mg/L), S = final substrate concentration (mg/L), X = initial biomass concentration (mg/L), X' = final biomass concentration (mg/L), θ = batch detention time (day), k = maximum substrate utilization rate (day⁻¹), K_s = half velocity constant (mg/L), Y = yield coefficient

and K_d = endogenous decay rate (day⁻¹).

In order to determine the kinetic constants 'K_s' and 'k', the values of [(θ.X)/(S₀ - S)] can be plotted with respect to (1/S). The plot of [(θ.X)/(S₀ - S)] versus (1/S) will be straight line, the slope and intercept of which represent (K_s/k) and (1/k) respectively. Once, the value of 'k' is obtained, K_s can be determined from the above plot. Similarly, the values of [(X' - X)/θX] can be plotted with respect to [(S₀ - S)/θX] to find out the kinetic constants 'Y' and 'k_d'. The plot of [(X' - X)/θX] versus [(S₀ - S)/θS] will be a straight line, the slope and intercept of which represent the kinetic constants 'Y' and 'k_d' respectively.

Kinetic study:

The Monod kinetic model as stated earlier was used to evaluate the performance of the reactor towards the biomass growth and degradation of substrates. The kinetic parameters such as maximum specific growth rate (k), yield coefficient (Y), half saturation concentration (K_s) and endogenous decay co-efficient (k_d) were determined by fitting the batch experiment data to those kinetic models through optimization using Microsoft Excel solver program. The kinetic model showing the best fit was selected with corresponding set of kinetic parameters. Experimental value of substrate and bio-mass concentration with the model predicted values at different time intervals were compared by optimization method.

Results and discussion

Batch acclimation study:

The detailed results of regular monitoring under the batch acclimation study are presented in Table 4. It is evident from the batch acclimation study that the anaerobic reactor was gradually improving the COD removal efficiency even under increasing amount of input COD concentration. Consequently, the acclimated biomass was also grown up along with the active microorganisms, which have been reflected in MLSS and MLVSS respectively. Bio-gas production was also observed to be consistently increasing up to an optimum value and then started to decrease. However, the fraction of active microorganisms to

Table 4. Results of batch acclimation study in the anaerobic tubular reactor

Acclimation run No.	Vol. raw WW (ml)	Vol. syn. WW (ml)	Initial pH	Final pH	Batch period (h)	Initial COD (mg/L)	Final COD (mg/L)	COD removal efficiency (%)	MLSS (mg/L)	Biogas (in Lit.)
1	50	450	7.07	7.26	72	2496	1184	52.56	10140	0.094
2	100	400	7.03	7.31	72	3888	1642	57.77	11260	0.146
3	150	350	7.06	7.41	72	4224	1640	61.17	13215	0.191
4	200	300	7.13	7.39	72	4503	1653	63.29	14850	0.253
5	250	250	7.03	7.29	72	4960	1638	66.97	16475	0.318
6	300	200	7.09	7.32	72	5340	1568	70.63	18125	0.389
7	350	150	7.08	7.28	72	5580	1343	75.93	20355	0.484
8	400	100	7.06	7.25	72	5728	1198	79.08	23810	0.626
9	450	50	7.12	7.34	72	5920	1172	80.2	25625	0.716

Table 5. Performance results of batch study in the anaerobic tubular reactor

Batch run No.	Vol. raw WW (ml)	Vol. syn. WW (ml)	Initial pH	Final pH	Batch period (h)	Initial COD (mg/L)	Final COD (mg/L)	COD removal efficiency (%)	MLSS (mg/L)	Biogas (in Lit.)
10	500	0	7.09	7.39	72	6140	1069	82.58	27790	0.714
11	600	0	7.06	7.24	72	6384	971	84.79	28920	0.781
12	700	0	7.08	7.33	72	6544	825	87.39	29615	0.816
13	800	0	7.05	7.39	72	6860	741	89.19	31240	0.839
14	900	0	7.02	7.24	72	7016	660	90.59	32635	0.884
15	1000	0	7.04	7.29	72	7238	522	92.78	33730	0.922
16	1100	0	7.08	7.32	72	7580	1600	78.89	31140	0.683
17	1200	0	7.16	7.43	72	7910	2570	67.5	29875	0.548

the total biomass varied marginally throughout the acclimation phase. It is obviously due to proportional increase of active microorganisms in the amount of anaerobic biomass.

Batch performance of the anaerobic reactor:

The detailed results of performance under batch kinetic study are presented in Table 5. It shows that the anaerobic reactor was becoming more and more capable for treating raw slaughterhouse wastewater. The profile of pH under batch operation of the anaerobic reactor is presented by bar diagram as shown in Fig. 3. The fluctuation in pH was nominal in all the batch runs, indicating stable function of the anaerobic reactor. The profile of initial and final COD as well as COD removal efficiency is also presented by bar diagram as shown in Fig. 4. COD removal efficiency was increasing up to a maximum value of 92.55% for an addition of 1000 ml raw wastewater

Fig. 3. pH Profile under batch operation of anaerobic reactor.

and then it reduced to 67.5% for similar addition of 1200 ml.

Both MLSS and MLVSS concentrations are observed to be increasing first and then gradually decreasing with the enhancement in quantity of raw wastewater. Consequently, the (MLVSS to MLSS)

Fig. 4. COD Profile under batch operation of anaerobic reactor.

ratio marginally increased to 0.27 and then it decreased to 0.22, indicating inhibition beyond a certain initial COD concentration. The profile of biogas (especially CH₄) is highlighted by bar diagram as shown in Fig. 5. It clearly indicates that the biogas production was continually decreasing with the increase in amount of raw wastewater, in turn enhancement in initial COD concentration.

Fig. 5. Biogas production profile under batch operation of anaerobic reactor.

Determination of kinetic co-efficients:

In order to develop substrate (COD) removal kinetics, firstly the values of $[(\theta.X)]/(S_0 - S)$ are plotted with respect to $(1/S)$ as shown in Fig. 6. Finally, to develop the growth kinetics, the values of $[(X' - X)/\theta X]$ are plotted with respect to $[(S_0 - S)/\theta X]$ as shown in Fig. 7. Therefore, growth kinetic constants i.e. maximum substrate utilization rate (k) and

Fig. 6. Determination of maximum substrate utilization rate (k) and half velocity constant (K_s).

Fig. 7. Determination of yield coefficient (Y) and endogenous decay constant (K_d).

half velocity constant (K_s), were figured as 0.2539 g COD/g VSS/day and 1.302 g COD/L respectively in accordance with eq. (1). The yield co-efficient ' Y ' and endogenous decay constant ' k_d ' were estimated as 0.239 g VSS/g COD removal and 0.013 g VSS/g VSS/day the respectively from eq. (2) with good curve fitting.

The maximum specific COD removal rate was determined as 0.2539 g COD/g VSS/day, which has not been reported so far elsewhere. This value indicates a low specific rate of COD removal in comparison to 1.47 g COD/g VSS/day as observed by Borja *et al.*¹³. The half-saturation constant i.e. K_s was found to be 1.302 g COD/L, which is also not reported so far in case of anaerobic treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater. The yield co-efficient (Y)

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was observed to be 0.239 day^{-1} , which almost corroborates the result reported by Borja *et al.*¹³ as $0.17 \text{ g VSS/g COD removed/day}$. Under the growth kinetics, the endogenous decay constant was obtained as $0.013/\text{day}$, which almost tallies with the similar observation made by Borja *et al.*¹³ as $0.029/\text{day}$.

Conclusion

It can be inferred from the present study that carbonaceous organics of raw slaughterhouse wastewater could be treated satisfactorily by tubular anaerobic reactor, provided adequate dilution is made. The maximum COD removal efficiency could be as high as 92.68% under a batch detention time of 3 days and a dilution ratio of 1:7. In the present study, maximum substrate utilization rate (k) and half velocity constant (K_s), are partially comparable with earlier finding. In addition, yield co-efficient (Y) and endogenous decay rate (K_d) also partially corroborate with the respective data available from literature. All these kinetic co-efficients would be extremely needful for designing the anaerobic reactor unit, treating slaughterhouse wastewater in the real field.

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